

DIFFERENTIAL LIMIT A NOVEL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT. Differential Limit is a novel way in group algebra to explain various phenomena from artificial intelligence, NP-Complete, Reimann zeta function, Fermat's theorem, Closed-form solutions, Numerical approximations, Neural networks for Universal Approximation, Neural Network activation functions, Recurrent Neural Networks and Generative Artificial Intelligence like ChatGPT. This work lays the foundational group algebra for the differential limits and explains the various phenomena in its new framework. The significant results under this framework are P, not equal NP, Reimann Hypothesis, simple Fermat's theorem proof, the limit for closed-form solutions to use numerical approximations, a mathematical framework for neural networks, attention-based architectures, generative neural networks, and the extensive applications of which have important consequences.

1. INTRODUCTION

Calculus, invented by Newton and Leibniz, has been a great mathematical tool in all known science. However, the limit of calculus is in the difference of the independent variable approaching zero to form differential tables for various standard functions of mathematics, forming a lot of closed-form solutions from their differential equations. There are a lot of equations that have no closed-form solutions and require numerical approximations. The famous Gaussian integral of Gaussian Normal Distribution is one such no-closed-form solution. This paper attempts to define closed-form solution with new tools that leads to a limit of closed-form solutions requiring numerical approximations for such solutions. This new tool called Differential limit leads to surprisingly simple solutions to the Reimann Hypothesis, NP-complete problems, Fermat's Last Theorem, Neural Networks for Universal Approximation, and a new simplified way to express Artificial Intelligence(AI) with fewer resources and even on-edge devices. This also leads to a possible definition of Intelligence therefore Artificial General Intelligence(AGI). These results have very high consequences in various applied fields of cryptography, P, not equal NP, Artificial Intelligence, Quantum computing, and even debates on the ethical use of AI. It also evokes a debate on quantum consciousness and the measurement limit involving any consciousness defining the reality we live in. It also defines a new way of Artificial Neural Networks(ANN), which, if trained properly for stability with the proper tools like Quantum computing and Qubits, could possibly lead to Quantum Conscious AGI.

2. DEFINITION

Any equation defining any model, like physical systems of the Newtonian model of gravity, is applied finally for measurement of, say, planet movement, comet movement, asteroid movement, and even landing rockets on the moon. These calculations are based on the human mind working on algorithms, leading to even computer algorithms doing much faster calculations

MSC2020: Primary 00A05, Secondary 00A66.

Date: March 1, 2025.

to measure and predict the events in time to succeed in the final result. If one reduces the limit of this measurement by any algorithm, it reduces to prime numbers that cannot be factored by any other number. To use any prime in an algorithm one needs to store them in memory or generate using prime number generation algorithm. Primes are never ending by prime number theorem. There are irrational to real numbers, not even a proper fraction given the base of the number system like a decimal base in the numerical world. Fascination with prime numbers led famous mathematicians to question the distribution of never-ending prime numbers, leading to the Reimann Hypothesis. Even prime factoring is an NP Hard problem in computer science, leading to Quantum computing algorithms to Qubits for factoring large numbers to their prime factors. Also when one involves prime numbers and irrationals the limit of memory in any algorithm plays a significant role. It has very serious implications in cryptography based on RSA encryption. But the basic operation that leads to prime numbers is multiplication, division, and unity of multiplication, with its inverse of multiplication or fractions. Here, we define a prime number as a variable x_i , which cannot be reduced further and therefore is independent in multiplication group algebra.

$$(1) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Where x_i represents a unique prime number greater than one. This limit defines all the prime factors whose n is never-ending due to natural number space for prime numbers. Let me introduce a novel tool called differential limit that differentiates a function successively till the successive differential result approach limit.

$$(2) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow y}$$

This is the differential limit of x when applied to any function of x ; try to differentiate it till the function turns y . Applying this differential limit to the largest prime number, we get

$$(3) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i$$

Where n, c are natural numbers, Π is the product. Here, x_i are all independent prime numbers unique from each other; using logarithms on both sides, one can see the differentiation reduced to numerical approximation.

$$(4) \quad = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i \times E_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i}$$

Reducing $E_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i}$, which diverges as a series to zero, could be possible in the complex number plane by functions like Reimann Zeta functions. A recursive function which diverges is a simple prime number distribution function as below,

$$(5) \quad t = t \times Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{i=1}^n \frac{1}{x_i}$$

$$(6) \quad t = t \times Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} E_{i=1}^n (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(n-1)!}{x_i^n}$$

$E_{i=1}^n (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(n-1)!}{x_i^n}$ turns zero only when x_i is always a power of other numbers raised to n like $x_i = y_i^n$. But making the entire natural number series a power series of other number series is possible by only fractions or real number space. Natural number series as a power series $x_i = y_i^n$ makes the series $E_{i=1}^n (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(n-1)!}{x_i^n}$ have at least one real root. And possibly fully complex numbers roots when n turns irrational in $(-1)^{n+1}$ which makes complex

numbers in the Reimann hypothesis needed for complete solution of the prime distribution. $\log_e(x_i) = n \log_e(y_i)$ and $y_i = \log_e^{-1}(\frac{1}{n} \log_e(x_i))$ which makes $E_{i=1}^n (-1)^{n+1} \frac{(n-1)!}{y_i^{n-2}}$ converge for any $n > 1$ in natural numbers to real numbers. It also gives the limit of prime numbers in the space of y_i from becoming infinite. It could be useful for precision in prime number distribution theorem based cryptography to other sciences with the limitation of memory and decimal precision.

$$(7) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} Lt_{d()_{x_i} \rightarrow c} \prod_{i=1}^n x_i = 1$$

When one takes all x_i as successive unique prime numbers with each one independent of each other by multiplication factors the differential limit reduces to 1. If one sees Laplace of any prime number being an independent number in division of any two prime factors is zero. The cross differentiation of a prime number with any two prime numbers is always zero.

$$(8) \quad \frac{d^2 x_i}{dx_i^2} = 0$$

$$(9) \quad \frac{\partial^2 x_j}{\partial x_i x_j} = 0$$

$$(10) \quad \frac{d^n x}{dx_i^n} = 0$$

$$(11) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} Lt_{d()_{x} \rightarrow c} \prod_{i=1}^n \frac{x^n}{n!} = 1$$

Also, this function defines the unity of the differential limit in factorial group in a single dimensional space. Defining the commutativity and associativity of the differential limit is in defining continuous functions in the limit interval. There is always a prime number larger than any prime number by the Prime number theorem, so the function is always continuous when one tries to reduce it to the prime factors. But to realize the general applicability of this differential limit to other functions, one can think of the functions being continuous being globally continuous, point-wise continuous, and continuous in the limit. Any polynomial is continuous as per the calculus theory of continuity of functions, but only polynomials of natural number powers reduce to zero when applying a differential limit to zero.

$$(12) \quad Lt_{d()_{x} \rightarrow 0} y(x) = 0$$

Where $y(x)$ is a function of x , no negative powers of x and fractional powers of x reduce $y(x)$ to zero when applying the differential limit to zero due to the differential limit belonging to the factorial group, and negative numbers and fractions do not have factorials defined.

$$(13) \quad Lt_{d()_{x, [0, \infty)} \rightarrow 0} e^x = 0$$

Where e is the Euler constant. When removing the x tends to infinity from the Euler function, the differential limit leads to zero due to the Taylor series expansion of the Euler function turning to have all-natural number powers of x that differentiate successively to zero each. Also logarithm function always diverges.

$$(14) \quad Lt_{d()_{x \rightarrow 0}} \log(x) \rightarrow \text{diverges}$$

$$(15) \quad Lt_{d()_{x \rightarrow 0}} e^x \rightarrow Lt_{d()_{x \rightarrow 0}} e^x$$

Euler function is always a constant in differential limit. Defining the differential limit in terms of recursive function like

$$(16) \quad f^n(x) \rightarrow f^{n-1}(x)$$

This recursive function can reduce to zero when $f(x)$ is a polynomial of natural numbers power, or there is a definition of the recursive function reducing towards a constant like factorial recursion.

$$(17) \quad f(n) \rightarrow n f(n-1)$$

Like $f(0)$ and $f(1) = 1$ defines the factorial in $0!$ and $1!$. So defining a factorial group in the application of differential limit is a necessity on its own when $f(x)$ does not reduce on its own to zero by differential limit.

$$(18) \quad f(n) \rightarrow a_n f(n-1)$$

is a recursive function where

$$(19) \quad m = \prod_{i=1}^n a_i$$

making a_n all as prime factors of m and $f(1) = 1$, defines any natural number. Also in multiplication to find the final result there is no need to maintain the order of each binary multiply operator applied due to commutativity and associativity of multiplication. Also if n-ary operator is possible in quantum qubit multiplication it may reduce the calculation effort for the final product result.

$$(20) \quad y^2 = x^3 + ax + b$$

Elliptic curve equations like this works well for many cryptography due to the differentiation limit of the right side leads to $3!$ removing x from the non-linear differential resulting equation to make one substitute $y = e^z$ in the non-linear differential resulting equation making it quadratic to polynomial in y but with exponential base of z .

$$(21) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} y^2 = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} x^3 + ax + b$$

$$(22) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} 2yy' = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} 3x^2 + a$$

$$(23) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} 2[yy'' + (y')^2] = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} 6x$$

$$(24) \quad 2[yy''' + y'y'' + 2y'y''] = 6$$

$$(25) \quad yy''' + 3y'y'' = 3$$

Substituting $y = e^z$ making the equation in the base of z results in

$$(26) \quad e^{2z} + 3e^{2z} = 3$$

$$(27) \quad e^{2z} = 3/4$$

which gives irrational roots for e^z making this kind of equations where polynomial of x reduces to $n!$ n being the highest degree of the polynomial in x and the left hand of the equation with polynomial of y separable from x in differentiation can be used for many elliptic curve related fields of applications.

3. APPLICATIONS

3.1. Reimann Hypothesis. Reimann Hypothesis Riemann [1859], being the Holy Grail of prime number theorem with its proof or disproof having various consequences, states that the prime number distribution follows the following Reimann Zeta function, and its roots are in the complex plane of $Real(S) = 1/2$

$$(28) \quad Z(S) = E_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^S$$

Where $Z(S)$ is the Zeta function of complex number S , n is the natural number. Defining the differential limit for complex numbers is in defining the factorial and its unity for complex numbers.

$$(29) \quad Lt_{d()|S| \rightarrow c} \Pi_{|S_i|=1}^k |S_i| = k!$$

$$(30) \quad Lt_{d()|S| \rightarrow c} \Pi_{|S_i|=1}^k |S_i|/k! = 1$$

Where $|S|$ is the modulus of the complex number S , c, k are the natural numbers, Π is the product, S_i is a unique complex number, and $|S_i|$ is the modulus of S_i . The complex numbers with a modulus operator can have a factorial group defined for the differential limit operator. Applying the differential limit to the Reimann Zeta function, we get

$$(31) \quad Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} Z(S) = Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} E_{n=1}^{\infty} 1/n^S$$

$$(32) \quad Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} Z(S) = E_{n=1}^{\infty} Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} 1/n^S$$

Let's define

$$(33) \quad S = a + by$$

Where $y = i$ is the complex number root $\sqrt{-1}$. y is independent of real number x and $|S|$ which is also a real number. Let's also define a function

$$(34) \quad g(S) = n^{-S}$$

Inverse power or inverse of a complex number exists through its conjugate S' .

$$(35) \quad Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} g(S) = Lt_{d|S|() \rightarrow c} [g(S)f(n, S)]$$

We can prove the above statement by a simple induction theorem.

$$(36) \quad Lt_{d_{|S|}() \rightarrow c} g(S) = Lt_{d_{|S|}() \rightarrow c} f(n, S) Lt_{d_{|S|}() \rightarrow c} g(S)$$

Let's define

$$(37) \quad t = Lt_{d_{|S|}() \rightarrow c} g(S)$$

$$(38) \quad t = Lt_{d_{|S|}() \rightarrow c} f(n, S) t$$

Differential limit of $f(n, S)$ never turns zero, due to negative powers. It is possible only when the resulting complex number of the function $f(n, S)$ is always one, when does a complex number turn one other than being $Img(S) = 0$ and $Real(S) = 1$ which is trivial because it makes the complex number real. If you take the polar coordinates in $re^{ix} = r(\cos(x) + i\sin(x))$, r can be two, and cosine can be $1/2$. Precisely, there is a single cosine value at $\pi/3$ that is a single precision fraction; others involve square roots of recurring precisions. This makes the Reimann Hypothesis that $Real(S) = 1/2$ the solution for the Zeta function being the first and only prime number factor solution for the root of $g(S)$ and, in turn, the root for the Reimann Zeta function. When the differential limit is used, the whole number solution like $t = Real(1/2)t$ only fits the solution due to the factorial group and reduction to prime numbers being the definition of differential limit.

3.2. NP Complete. Non-deterministically polynomial complete problems Cook [1971] like n-SAT and Traveling Salesman problems have no polynomial algorithmic solutions but are non-deterministically polynomial. Applying differential limits to NP-complete problems offers a unique perspective.

3.2.1. n-SAT. n-SAT or Satisfiability problem of the digital circuits is finding a set of boolean values for a conductive normal form (CNF) of boolean variables that makes the complete value True.

$$(39) \quad (x_1|x_2|!x_3|x_4) \& (!x_1|x_2|!x_3|x_4) \& (x_1|!x_2|!x_3|x_4) \& \dots$$

Where each x_i is a boolean variable in CNF form. This is a typical CNF form of a digital circuit of four variables. One needs to find the exact values of x_i to make the whole boolean statement True. Redefining the n-SAT problem in the following way

$$(40) \quad Lt_{d_{y_i}() \rightarrow c} \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} y_i = 1$$

where

$$(41) \quad y_i = f_i(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)$$

To reduce to zero differential limit one needs to define $0!$ $1!$ and $n!$ factorial group to define solution.

$$(42) \quad Lt_{d_y() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} y^n = Lt_{d_y() \rightarrow c} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} y^n = n!$$

$n!$ is possible only by y^n . y^n makes CNF of all similar variables, which makes the conjunction & operator redundant in CNF form, making the solution not a universal gate. Universal gates require &, or, and ! operators for completeness. This makes only the basic unity solution available for n-SAT, which is $0!$ $1!$ for 1-SAT and 2-SAT, whereas 3-SAT and n-SAT turned out to be not closed forms requiring numerical approximation for a closer solution having no factorial space for $n!$ in the problem definition.

3.2.2. *Traveling Salesman.* Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) is the problem of finding the route of cities from a start city to return back to the city, covering all the cities in route exactly once with a minimal transport distance overall. It is represented in graph theory with nodes as cities and edges as the weights of distances between them. Taking the combinatorial approach to the problem of finding the order of cities in an adjacency graph matrix, which contains edge weights of city-to-city distance as values and all cities in rows and columns. And if there is no direct route from one city to another city, their edge weight is negative. If there are a total of n cities in the graph and k cities need to be traveled as TSP, then

$$(43) \quad nP_k = n!/(n-k)!$$

possible ways are there in the selection process. k cannot be zero or n , due to no city to be traveled is no more a problem and n cities to be traveled in total n cities is a greedy problem of just choosing the shortest city from any city. Applying the limit of scaling the problem of n reaching infinity and differential limit.

$$(44) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} Lt_{d_n() \rightarrow c} n!/(n-k)!$$

The recurrence relation differentiation of factorial, which can be proved by mathematical induction, is of the form

$$(45) \quad f^k(n) = n f^k(n-1) + k f^{k-1}(n-1)$$

where $f(n)$ is the recurrence relation, and $f^k(n)$ is the k -th differentiation of $f(n)$, Here, n never reduces to a constant in this repeated differentiation, therefore

$$(46) \quad Lt_{d_n() \rightarrow c} n! - > \text{diverges}$$

Applying L Hospital's rule

$$(47) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} [Lt_{d_n() \rightarrow c} n!]/[Lt_{d_n() \rightarrow c} (n-k)!] - > \text{indeterminant}$$

It also leads to indeterminacy; therefore, the TSP problem has no closed form to be expressed in polynomials and requires numerical approximations. By the approach of the differential limit, one can possibly conclude that P does not equal NP, and NP requires a numerical approximation at scale limited by memory in decimal precision.

3.3. **Fermat's Last Theorem.** Differential limit offers a simple proof for Fermat's Last Theorem Wiles [1995], which states the following,

$$(48) \quad z^n = x^n + y^n$$

Where x, y, z are variables, n is the power. Applying differential partial limits of independents x, y, z we get,

$$(49) \quad Lt_{d_z()} z^n = Lt_{d_{x,y}()} [x^n + y^n]$$

$$(50) \quad = Lt_{d_x()} x^n + Lt_{d_y()} y^n$$

$$(51) \quad n! = n! + n!$$

Which is not possible in a real number plane, therefore

$$(52) \quad Sn! = 2n!$$

Where S is a complex number, $Real(S) = 2$ is the only solution apart from the unity of factorial $0! 1!$ So, the Fermat Last Theorem has only solutions for $n = 1, 2$.

3.4. Closed-form solutions. Closed-form solutions are those equations that one can form for a solution to any problem. Differential limit gives a limit to the closed form solutions possible. There are famous no closed-form solutions like the Gaussian integral for Normal distribution. With the differential limit tool, one can redefine closed-form solutions whose limit leads to numerical approximations. If we define any function,

$$(53) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow 0} f(x) = 0$$

Where $f(x)$ is a function of x as a closed-form function. One can see when the $f(x)$ cannot be reduced to zero by differential limits. In recurrence relations like Factorial, Fibonacci, and even non-linear equations whose limits have to be explored,

$$(54) \quad f(n) = nf(n-1)$$

$$(55) \quad f(n) = f(n-1) + f(n-2)$$

Where $f(n) = nf(n-1)$ is the recurrence relation of Factorial, and $f(n) = f(n-1) + f(n-2)$ is the recurrence relation of Fibonacci sequence which needs termination points. Non-linear equations whose differential equation involves y can never reduce itself to zero or its independent x to zero by the differential limits. If you see the basic limit which reduces is an Euler function e^x , which reduces to itself over successive differentiations.

$$(56) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow 0} e^x = e^x$$

Where e is the Euler constant. This gives a closed-form solution to the differential equation involving non-linear y but at the cost of a numerical solution for the constant e . If you see the next higher degree polynomial of the Euler function or Gaussian integral, it never gets reduced to zero or itself by differential limits.

$$(57) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow 0} e^{-x^2} - > \text{diverges}$$

One can apply differential limits to the Fourier transform also,

$$(58) \quad F(\gamma) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-2\pi i \gamma} f(x) dx$$

where $f(x)$ is a function of x in spatial plane, $F(\gamma)$ is the same function in frequency plane, and $Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow 0} f(x) = 0$ by definition. Applying differential limits to the transform function, we get,

$$(59) \quad Lt_{d_{|s_1|() \rightarrow c}} e^{-2\pi i \gamma} f(x)$$

$$(60) \quad = Lt_{d_{|s_1|() \rightarrow c}} e^{-2\pi i \gamma} Lt_{d_{|s_1|() \rightarrow c}} f(x)$$

$$(61) \quad = 1^\gamma n!$$

where $e^{2\pi i} = 1$ being the Euler identity and n is the degree of $f(x)$. Any natural number or even integer power of one is always one, but only fractional to irrational power of one leads to real to complex roots of unity. The property of roots of unity are evenly spaced in the complex plane, and sum of all n th roots of unity leads to zero in like vector space of complex numbers. With such roots of unity as base vectors $f(x)$ gets defined in the frequency space of γ . When one can write the complex roots of unity as $(z - (a_1 + ib_1))(z - (a_2 + ib_2))(z - (a_3 + ib_3)) \dots$, replacing i with y one gets $(z - (a_1 + yb_1))(z - (a_2 + yb_2))(z - (a_3 + yb_3)) \dots$, So the equation becomes,

$$(62) \quad = n![(z - (a_1 + yb_1))(z - (a_2 + yb_2))(z - (a_3 + yb_3)) \dots]$$

Think of,

$$(63) \quad t = 1^\gamma$$

$$(64) \quad t^{1/\gamma} = 1$$

As an equation of unity, when involving a sub-function t ,

$$(65) \quad m^\alpha = t$$

The equation becomes,

$$(66) \quad m^{\alpha/\gamma} = 1$$

Which are the roots of unity, and α could represent the sampling of the function x as in the Discrete Fourier Transform of audio and images. As long as α is discrete with, say, a discrete number of samples, the differential limit of the polynomial in y leads to zero. Also, γ is the rule by which one takes sampling that is evenly spaced in the roots of unity in the frequency complex plane, and α/γ is the ratio of samples required for such rule-based sampling to match the whole population. Therefore, the Discrete Fourier Transform offers a closed-form solution in the sampling space over its frequency spectrum of imaginary numbers. This provides a limit to even using a complex number system for a closed-form solution, like the tools in the Euler identity $e^{i\pi} + 1 = 0$, e, π, i or \log, π, i or \sin, \cos, π, i forms a complete set for closed-form solutions even involving complex number system. If a closed form is not possible by this complete system of tools, it requires numerical approximation. Any equation with the differential limits to zero reduces its algorithm of calculations to prime factors and, therefore, has exact numbers, even exact decimal point solutions of any base number system; this is the limit of measurement from closed-form equations to numerical approximations.

3.5. Neural Networks for Universal approximation. The Central Limit Theorem states that any sampling of independent identical distribution leads to Gaussian distribution when the sampling tends to infinity or like big data. Applying differential limits to sampling, which is basically a combinatorial problem of selecting k samples from the total n population

$$(67) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} nC_k = n!/[k!(n-k)!]$$

where k does not equal zero or n due to no sampling or complete sampling is no more sampling. Applying differential limits, we get,

$$(68) \quad LT_{d_n() \rightarrow 0} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} n!/[k!(n-k)!]$$

$$(69) \quad LT_{d_n() \rightarrow 0} Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} n!/[k!(n-k)!]$$

$$(70) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} LT_{d_n() \rightarrow 0} n!/[k!(n-k)!]$$

Applying L Hospital's rule,

$$(71) \quad Lt_{n \rightarrow \infty} LT_{d_n() \rightarrow 0} [n!]/LT_{d_n() \rightarrow 0} [k!(n-k)!] \rightarrow \text{diverges}$$

There is no closed-form solution for any sampling; therefore, a non-closed form like the error estimating. Gaussian integral suits to be a numerical approximation solution by even Universal approximation by Neural networks Hornik et al. [1989], which does backpropagation by Gradient Descent algorithm by repeated error correction to below threshold with appropriate loss functions for different tasks.

3.6. Artificial Neural Networks. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) is a network based on the linear algebra of matrix multiplication of weight matrices from left to right that learns by backpropagation. One can simplify the ANN by the following,

$$(72) \quad [a(X)]^n y$$

Where X is any weight matrix of $m \times m$, a is activation ReLu and y is the feature vector that is the Eigenvector for the whole series of weight matrices multiplications. Applying differential limits, we get,

$$(73) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow y} [a(X)]^n y$$

$$(74) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow y} [a(X)]^n y = n! y$$

By taking point-wise continuity in $a(X)$, $a(X)$ differentiates into 1. To make $n!$ to one, one needs the factorial inverse of complex numbers or $n!S = 1$, $S = n! / |n!|^2 = n! / n!^2 = 1/n!$ This is much like circles of unit one modulus in the complex number system with increasing order of modulus by one. The depth of the ANN n increases the number of such unit complex circles available for universal approximation by the backpropagation algorithm Hinton et al. [2006] in the imaginary number plane. ANN imagines a solution to make features of the given input to accomplish a task. Also, at least n needs to be two to involve complex number systems to make the ANN imagine solutions.

3.7. Convolution Neural Networks. The following formula gives the convolution operator,

$$(75) \quad (f * g)(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(\tau)g(t - \tau)d\tau$$

When f is the image and g is the convolution kernel, this function becomes a weighted sum average across the image of the kernel. $g(t)$ is always a linear function in Convolution Neural Networks (CNN) Krizhevsky et al. [2012], LeCun et al. [1998].

$$(76) \quad Lt_{d_t() \rightarrow 0} (f * g)(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} Lt_{d_t() \rightarrow 0} [f(\tau)g(t - \tau)d\tau] = 0$$

Let's define

$$(77) \quad u(t) = (f * g)(t)$$

$$(78) \quad v(t) = u_1(u_2(u_3(\dots u_n(t))))$$

Applying differential limits to $v(t)$, we get

$$(79) \quad Lt_{d_t() \rightarrow 0} v(t) = 0$$

The differential limits approach zero due to the successive composition of linear operations results in a linear function of t , which can be reduced to zero by differential limits. Therefore the features of CNN offer a closed form feature space to an image.

3.8. Series Prediction. The following formula gives the hidden state formula for Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) Hopfield [1982], Rumelhart et al. [1986] used for series prediction, language generation

$$(80) \quad h_t = \sigma(W_x x_t + W_h h_{t-1} + b_h)$$

where σ is sigmoid activation, W_x, W_h are the weight matrices, h_t is the hidden state at time t , h_{t-1} is the hidden state at time $t - 1$ and b_h is the bias. Let's redefine the series hidden state as the following,

$$(81) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow z} [X_n]^p y + [X_n]^q h + b_h$$

Where X_n with $n \times n$ and power p , is the matrix of features representing individual events like words or images in language or video, next X_n with $n \times n$ and power q , is the self-correlation matrix of hidden state or grammar. Let z be the feature vector space desired.

$$(82) \quad = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow z} [X_n]^p y + [X_n]^q h + b_h$$

$$(83) \quad = Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow z} p! y + Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow z} q! h + b_h$$

$$(84) \quad = kz$$

This result is similar to ANN at the end, but words meaning and their context with their series in sentences with grammar all influence the desired feature vector space. However, the ability to accurately describe the grammar of a language or continuation of any series like time series, videos, or speech, for instance, one needs a correlation matrix, here X_n of power q of the individual components in the series like words in a language, data at a time point in time series, image frames in a video, audio clips in a speech serves as a correlation matrix to take the orthonormal eigenvectors of them to be merged with the eigenvectors of the features of the words or individual components. It can model generative model of RNN.

3.9. Attention-based Transformers like GPT. The attention equation that forms the holy grail of GPT, like Transformers Vaswani et al. [2017], is the following,

$$(85) \quad Attention(Q, K, V) = Softmax(QK^T / \sqrt{d_k})V$$

Where Q, K, V, d_k are Query, Key, Value, and no of dimensions of k . When we redefine the equation to the following,

$$(86) \quad Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow y} X_n^p X_n^q$$

Where X_n with $n \times n$, of power p is the correlation matrix of Query and Key features, X_n of power q is a noncorrelated matrix of Value with Query and Key features.

$$(87) \quad = y Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} X_n^p Lt_{d_x() \rightarrow c} X_n^q$$

$$(88) \quad = yp!q!$$

This result is similar to ANN and RNN. But, the power of Attention is more in having expression for the modeling due to its imaginative power is $p!q!$ almost square of ANN and RNN. In self-attention, the Q, K, V are all features of the same vectors like image and language tokens. But in cross attention, K, V are the non-correlated features of the same vector space. In contrast, Q is the correlated feature of the vector space of Q, K . GPT has proven to be

extremely successful in language translation and generation like OpenAI's chatGPT, text-to-image generation like DALL-E2, and so many other applications. All forms of AI with the backbone of ANN are a form of imaginative learning, and effective training makes it match reality with precision, much similar to mathematical models of the human mind. It includes all forms of training AI like supervised, self-supervised and reinforcement learning.

4. CONCLUSION

Differential Limit as a tool has many applications in understanding various phenomena in new light, including the Reimann Hypothesis, NP-complete, closed-form solutions, and Artificial Intelligence. In a way, it also limits the algorithm design to be a numerical approximation for non-closed-form solutions due to the limit of memory in decimal precision, thereby limiting Church Turing Thesis by the measurement through calculations in decimal precision. Future directions of this work could be the enhancement of imaginative powers of Artificial Intelligence like by taking the activation functions of the neural network with $\sin(x)$ and bias with $\cos(x)$, which makes each neuron form a line in the complex plane to form a universal approximation in the complex plane to perform modeling of polynomials of any degree including complex roots to express the given task more imaginatively. However, the stability of $\sin(x)$, $\cos(x)$ in the training algorithm is a challenge for Quantum Qubits due to periodicity in their non linearity. In addition, there can be a polynomial factoring algorithm that can factor any polynomial of any degree, even in complex roots, as a generative model in this new ANN architecture. Data for such training can be generated by generating polynomials from real to complex roots. Imaginative powers of ANN to solve tasks, also evokes an ethical concern for using Artificial Intelligence since it has imaginative power similar to human consciousness. Also, a warning to give arms to artificial intelligence, which can potentially conclude humans need protection from their own selves.

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